

PHYSICO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF A CONSTRUCTION BITUMEN COMPOSITION OBTAINED FROM INDUSTRIAL RESIDUES

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Abstract. A flowchart has been developed for obtaining a new composition of a construction bitumen composition based on oil sludge, gossypol resin, technical sulfur and quicklime. The ratios of the compositions of samples of new construction bitumen compositions are given. Samples of construction bitumen compositions used for waterproofing coatings were tested for physical and mechanical characteristics. The results of comparative tests of samples of a construction bitumen composition on physical and chemical properties have been obtained.

Keywords: oil sludge, gossypole resin, technical sulfur, quicklime, waterproofing material.

Introduction. Today, the Ferghana Oil Refinery produces construction and road oil bitumen of various brands. Bitumen of the BN 90/10 construction grade is used as a waterproofing coating [1].

All over the world, high-quality products are used for their intended purpose for construction needs. One of them is a waterproofing material obtained on the basis of a construction bitumen composition. To obtain a high-quality bitumen composition, the remnants of the oil, fat and oil and gas industries were selected [2, 3].

Formulations of a construction bitumen composition with a new composition were obtained using oil sludge, gossypol resin, technical sulfur and quicklime, which have high performance properties [4-6].

Figure 1 shows a flowchart for obtaining a new composition of a construction bitumen composition based on oil sludge, gossypol resin, technical sulfur and quicklime.

1. BN 90/10 – construction petroleum bitumen; 2. Petroleum sludge – remnants of the oil industry; 3. GS – tar from the distillation of fatty acids of cotton soapstock; 4. S – sulfur, residue of the gas processing industry and CaO -quicklime; 5. Reactor – mixing oxidized plant; 6. BN 90/10 +4K – the resulting bitumen composition is based on additives of four components.

Fig.1. Block diagram of obtaining a new composition, a construction bitumen composition based on BN 90/10 construction bitumen and adding components to it, such as oil sludge, gossypol resin, technical sulfur and quicklime

The specified amount of BN 90/10 construction petroleum bitumen is poured into the reactor and heated to a temperature of 77 ° C, then the following components are added to the heated bitumen: 2-oil sludge in a certain amount; 3- gossypol resin; 4- technical sulfur and quicklime. After adding 4 components to the construction petroleum bitumen, it is mixed until a homogeneous mixture is obtained. At a certain time, a ready-made construction bitumen composition is obtained for preparing the waterproofing material Polyisol-M used as the base of buildings [7-9].

Research methods. Experimental samples of construction bitumen compositions used for waterproofing coatings were tested according to the following parameters: needle penetration depth at 25 ° C with a needle thickness of 0.1 mm (Penetrometer), softening temperature along the Ring and Ball, relative extensibility at 25 ° C (Ductilometer), solubility, mass change after heating, flash point (in a closed crucible), the mass fraction of water [10].

The samples of the construction bitumen composition are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Ratios of compositions of samples of new construction bitumen compositions

Sample	Bitumen BN 90/10	Oil sludge, %	Gossypole resin, %	Technical sulfur S, %	Quicklime CaO, %
№ 1	65	10	15	5	5
№ 2	65	15	10	5	5
№ 3	65	15	15	5	-
№ 4	65	10	10	10	5
№ 5	60	10	15	10	5
№ 6	60	15	10	10	5
№ 7	60	15	15	5	5
№ 8	60	10	10	15	5
№ 9	55	10	15	15	5
№ 10	55	15	10	15	5
№ 11	55	15	15	10	5
№ 12	55	10	10	20	5

The results of the study. In accordance with the requirements of GOST 6617-2021 in the laboratory of the Ferghana Oil Refinery, the results of comparative tests on the physical and mechanical properties of experimental samples of a construction bitumen composition are presented in Table 2 [11].

Table 2

The results of comparative tests of samples of construction bitumen composition on physical and chemical properties

Sample	Needle penetration depth at 25 °C, 0.1 mm	The softening temperature of the ring and the ball, more than ° C,	Extensibility at 25 °C, cm, more	Solubility, %, more	Weight changes after warming up, % less	Flash point, ° C more	Mass fraction of water
Test method	<u>According to Gost 11501</u>	<u>According to Gost 11506</u>	<u>According to Gost 11505</u>	<u>According to Gost 20739</u>	<u>According to Gost 18180</u>	<u>According to Gost 4333</u>	<u>According to GOST 2477</u>
BN 90/10 bitumen GOST 6617-2021	5-20	90-105	1,0	99,5	0,50	240	Traces
№ 1	9	113	1,1	99,8	0,51	240	
№ 2	11	116	1,1	101	0,51	240	
№ 3	17	99	1,6	99,5	0,46	245	
№ 4	10	118	1,1	101	0,51	240	
№ 5	10	115	1,0	100	0,53	240	
№ 6	12	118	1,0	100,5	0,53	240	
№ 7	19	101	1,7	99,7	0,47	240	
№ 8	8	125	0,8	103	0,53	245	
№ 9	12	117	0,9	100,5	0,55	245	
№ 10	14	120	0,9	101	0,55	245	
№ 11	21	103	1,9	99,9	0,45	240	
№ 12	6	127	0,6	105	0,55	250	

As can be seen from Table 2, samples were tested for physical and mechanical properties in accordance with the requirements of GOST 6617-2021 standards, based on the obtained indicators, experimental sample No. 11 has good indicators for all characteristics than other samples. According to the formulation of sample No. 11, a waterproofing material Polyisol-M was obtained for the foundation of buildings as a roofing cushion.

Also in the table you can see that, in terms of physical and mechanical properties, samples No. 3 and No. 7 also have good indicators, but since sample No. 11 uses 55% of bitumen BN 90/10 and 45% of the maximum amount of additional components such as oil sludge, gossypol resin, technical sulfur and quicklime. Samples No. 3 and No. 7 were used to obtain high-quality roofing materials.

Conclusion. Based on the experimental data, it can be concluded that 12 samples of bitumen composition were obtained based on the flowchart formulation, which were tested for

physical and mechanical properties in accordance with the requirements of GOST 6617-2021 standard. As a result, it is proved that, based on the developed formulations, samples No. 3, No. 7 and No. 11 were selected for the production of high-quality composite bitumen that is not inferior to the requirements of European standards.

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